

PROPOSALS FOR A COMMON TURKIC ALPHABET AND THE CREATION OF A COMMON TURKIC WRITING SYSTEM “ORTABITIK”

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To solve the problems of alphabets and writing of Turkic languages, we propose to create a writing system “ortabitik” [1, 2, 3, 4], that is, four isomorphic alphabet systems: 1) an alphabet based on the Latin alphabet; 2) an alphabet based on the Cyrillic alphabet; 3) an alphabet based on the Arabic alphabet; 4) an alphabet based on the Orkhon-Yenisei script. In the Turkic group of languages there are 39 phonemes in total, in each national Turkic language there are approximately 30-35 phonemes of these 39 phonemes in different samples. For 39 Turkic phonemes we propose to introduce 39 different graphemes in each of the above-mentioned alphabets. Based on the isomorphism of these four alphabet systems, there is a real possibility to create programs for precise automatic transliteration and transcription of text in one alphabet into text in another alphabet. This will allow each Turkic-speaking person to easily study, in addition to the 30-35 phonemes and graphemes of their native language, another 4-9 phonemes and graphemes that do not exist in their native language, and on this basis, a Turkic-speaking person will be able to read texts in all Turkic languages written in any of the alphabets. All information in all Turkic languages of the Turkic civilization will be able to be united by these alphabets as a holistic writing system. At the same time, the Ortaturk language [5, 6, 7, 8] will also have its own set of phonemes and graphemes in this system, which will include those phonemes and graphemes that are available to the majority of Turkic nations, the majority of Turkic-speaking individuals, for the longest period of time. And also provide the greatest measure of semantic adequacy of lexemes in most Turkic languages. In the Ortaturk language, it will be possible to collect all the information significant for the Turkic civilization, and this information resource will be very large, no less than required for an international language.

The overwhelming majority of texts in national Turkic languages are composed in one of the variants of these alphabets, and its variants in all other basic alphabets

are generated by means of error-free automatic transliteration due to the isomorphism of these alphabets. A person who can read one of the national Turkic languages can read a text in the alphabet that is convenient for him in accordance with his reading skills. Of the total number of 39 phonemes of the Turkic languages, each Turkic national language has a certain number of phonemes in its phonetic system. Each Turkic language uses graphemes associated with these phonemes in its alphabet.

There are 73 symbols in “The Old Turkic Letter Yenisei” system. To express the 39 phonemes existing in the Turkic languages and form the new Orkhon-Yenisei script “The New Turkic Letter Yenisei”, it is necessary to select the corresponding graphemes for this new Orkhon-Yenisei script from these 73 symbols. Considering that many of the symbols of the Orkhon-Yenisei script are used to express syllables, and also that for a number of Turkic phonemes there are no corresponding graphemes in the Old Orkhon-Yenisei script, it will be necessary to add a number of new graphemes. For example, in order to express the vowel harmony that exists in the vast majority of Turkic languages and will exist in the future in the Ortaturk language standard, in “The New Turkic Letter Yenisei”, in addition to the four graphemes that existed for vowels in the Old Orkhon-Yenisei script, four new graphemes should be introduced for the vowels that correspond vowel harmony. They can be created by drawing an additional horizontal line over the four graphemes of “The Old Turkic Letter Yenisei” alphabet that express vowels.

For some other sounds that do not have a symbol in the Orkhon-Yenisei script, a more suitable symbol can be selected from the 73 symbols present in it.

I think it would be better if this solution to the problem of the alphabet of the Turkic languages was called "ortabitik", because if we call this writing system "ortaalifbo", then in many Turkic languages there is no such word as "alifbo", if we call it "ortaalphabet" it will be as if the Turkic languages did not have their own writing and alphabet from ancient times. "Ortabitik" will be convenient for all Turkic peoples, since the Turkic peoples in the modern era use the Latin, Cyrillic and Arabic alphabets, and they will have the opportunity to use the information resource of the information space of the entire Turkic civilization in the alphabet.

The Commission for the Creation of a Unified Turkic Alphabet formed under the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) submitted a draft of The Common Turkic alphabet for consideration by the higher bodies of the OTS, which is given in **Table No. 1**. This project primarily takes into account the alphabets of the languages of the Turkic nations, whose states are members of the OTS, therefore the project provides for the consideration of only 34 phonemes, not 39. But in the future it can be supplemented with specific phonemes that exist in languages of other Turkic nations, and for them, corresponding additional graphemes can also be introduced.

This draft was submitted to the secretariat of the Organization of Turkic States and will be considered at the Summit of the Heads of State of the Organization of Turkic States. On the eve of the Summit, the Turan Academy of Sciences and its Ortaturk Language Scientific Research Institute held a number of scientific conferences to collect proposals from scientists, and my following proposals were discussed and approved at them:

The project presented by the Commission for the creation of a common Turkic alphabet, organized by the Organization of Turkic States, is acceptable in principle, but we propose making some changes and additions:

1) We propose to assign one grapheme based on the Latin alphabet to each phoneme of the Turkic languages. In this project, it is planned to introduce two letters for one phoneme [æ] – (Ə ə) and (Ä ä). If to each of the 34 phonemes of the common Turkic alphabet does not correspond one grapheme, that is, if there is no isomorphism between phonemes and graphemes, that is, if there is no one-to-one correspondence between phonemes and graphemes, then in the process of digitizing the information resources of the Turkic languages, there will be no possibility of automatic error-free transliteration and error-free transcription, and additional human verification of all texts will be required.

2) The project does not plan a grapheme for the phoneme [ɒ], which exists in the Uzbek language. This phoneme [ɒ] is used in the main words of the Uzbek language, such as "Ota, Ота", ("Ota yurt, Ота юрт") and "Ona, Она" ("Ona Vatan, Она ВатаН"), in other Turkic languages these words are used in the form "Ata, Ата" and "Ana, АНА". For the correct pronunciation of these words, we propose adding the phoneme [ɒ] to the phoneme system of the common Turkic alphabet and propose representing it with a grapheme (Ä ä). In this case, the number of graphemes (and phonemes) in the common Turkic alphabet will increase from 34 to 35. If this is done, then to each of the 35 phonemes of the common Turkic alphabet will correspond one grapheme, that is, there will be isomorphism between the phonemes and graphemes, that is, a one-to-one correspondence. This isomorphism provides the possibility of automatic error-free transliteration and error-free transcription in the process of digitizing the information resources of the Turkic languages and is of fundamental importance from this point of view. We propose to place this grapheme (Ä ä) after the grapheme (A a) in the system of the Common Turkic alphabet.

3) If we accept the two above-mentioned provisions, the Common Turkic alphabet will consist of 35 graphemes and isomorphically corresponding phonemes. We propose to continue the Common Turkic alphabet based on the Latin alphabet, which has such an isomorphism, in the form of the Ortabitik writing system. In the Ortabitik writing system, for 35 phonemes are introduced 35 isomorphically

corresponding graphemes based on four writing systems: 1) based on the Latin alphabet; 2) based on the Cyrillic alphabet; 3) based on the Arabic alphabet; 4) based on the Orkhon-Yenisei script. The table of the Ortabitik writing system for Turkic languages is attached in **Table No. 2**.

Currently, the vast majority of texts written in Turkic languages exist in one of these four main alphabets, and the text variants in the other three main alphabets in the Ortabitik writing system are formed by automatic transliteration using computer transliteration and transcription programs, and an automatic error-free transcription of the text is also formed. A person speaking a Turkic language will be able to read a text in the alphabet he wants to read, and he will be able to read a text in the alphabet that matches his reading skills. Of the total 35 phonemes of the Turkic languages, each language of the Turkic people has a system of phonemes with a certain number and composition. This Turkic language uses graphemes associated with these phonemes in its alphabet. Each Turkic people will have its own priority alphabet, and the education system will be organized, books will be published, mass media will work, and office work will be conducted in this alphabet. As a result of digitalization, all this information will also be available in the form of electronic files that can be automatically generated in other alphabets. At the same time, all the heritage and information resources of the Turkic civilization will also be available in the alphabet based on the Orkhon-Yenisei script created by our ancestors.

The Turkic peoples currently use the Latin (Turkiye, Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan, partly Uzbekistan), Cyrillic (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, the Turkic republics and peoples of Russia, partly Uzbekistan), Arabic (Eastern Turkestan, Afghanistan, Iran, Saudi Arabia) alphabets. Many Turkic peoples who use the Cyrillic and Arabic alphabets have limited opportunities to study information in the Turkic Latin alphabet and, especially, to reform your alphabet into a Latin based alphabet. If the Ortabitik writing system is created, people who speak Turkic languages will be able to correctly read each other's information. At the same time, all the heritage and information resources of the Turkic civilization will be available in the alphabet based on the Orkhon-Yenisei script created by our ancestors. At the same time, these resources will also be available in international transcription, and all of Humanity will be able to pronounce them correctly. If each symbol in a certain text is replaced by its number from this table, then the text can be created in encrypted form as a set of numbers. A computer program for the Ortabitik system has been created and all of the above actions are performed automatically and without errors.

There are 73 symbols in the Old Turkic Letter Yenisei system. To express 35 phonemes existing in the Common Turkic Alphabet project and to form “The New Turkic Letter Yenisei”, it is necessary to select the corresponding graphemes for this

new Orkhon-Yenisei alphabet from these 73 symbols. Considering that many of the symbols of the Orkhon-Yenisei script are used to express syllables, and also that for a number of Turkic phonemes there are no corresponding graphemes in the Old Orkhon-Yenisei script, it will be necessary to add a number of new graphemes.

For example, in order to express the vowel harmony that exists in the absolute majority of Turkic languages and will exist in the future in the Ortaturk language standard [5, 6, 7, 8], in the new Orkhon-Yenisei script “The New Turkic Letter Yenisei”, in addition to the four graphemes that existed for vowels in the old Orkhon-Yenisei script, four new graphemes should be introduced for the vowels that correspond vowel harmony. They were created by drawing an additional horizontal line over each of the four graphemes of the old alphabet “The Old Turkic Letter Yenisei” that express vowels.

For some other phonemes that exist in modern Turkic languages, but did not have a phoneme and grapheme in the ancient Orkhon-Yenisei script, a grapheme from the 73 graphemes of this script was chosen that expressed the most consonant phoneme, and if it was necessary to preserve this selected grapheme itself, it was modified by adding an additional horizontal line. Consonants, represented in the ancient Orkhon-Yenisei script in all cases by the same grapheme, were adopted into “The New Turkic Letter Yenisei” alphabet. For consonant phonemes, represented in the ancient Orkhon-Yenisei script in different cases by a different grapheme, one of the grapheme variants was adopted into “The New Turkic Yenisei” alphabet.

As a result, the alphabetic principle was fully implemented in the new Orkhon-Yenisei script, while in the ancient Orkhon-Yenisei script the alphabetic and syllabic components existed together. Texts written in the new Orkhon-Yenisei script can be read, correctly pronounced and understood in most cases by those who know the old Orkhon-Yenisei script, since the differences in graphemes consist only in additional horizontal lines that function as diacritics. If the Organization of Turkic States supports the creation of this Ortabitik writing system, then it will be possible to form a single grapheme space, that is, a space of a single script, within the entire Turkic civilization.

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Table No.1

№	Graphemes based on the Latin alphabet	International transcription of phonemes
1	Aa	[a]
2	B b	[b]
3	C c	[dʒ]
4	Ç ç	[tʃ]
5	D d	[d]
6	E e	[e]
7	Ə ə, Ää	[æ]
8	F f	[f]
9	G g	[g]
10	Ğ ğ	[ɣ]
11	H h	[h]
12	X x	[χ]
13	I i	[ɯ]
14	İ i	[i]
15	J j	[ʒ]

№	Graphemes based on the Latin alphabet	International transcription of phonemes
20	N n	[n]
21	Ñ ñ	[ɲ]
22	O o	[o]
23	Ö ö	[ø]
24	P p	[p]
25	R r	[r]
26	S s	[s]
27	Ş ş	[ʃ]
28	T t	[t]
29	U u	[u]
30	Ū ū	[ʊ]
31	Ü ü	[y]
32	V v	[v]
33	Y y	[j]
34	Z z	[z]

16	K k	[k]
17	Q q	[q]
18	L l	[l]
19	M m	[m]

Table No. 2

№	Graphemes based on the Latin alphabet	International transcription of phonemes	Graphemes based on the Arabic alphabet	Graphemes based on the Kirill alphabet	Graphemes based on the Orxon-yenisey alphabet
1	Aa	[a]	ا	Аа	↯
2	Ää	[ɐ]	آ	Ää	↯
3	B b	[b]	ب	Б б	⋈
4	C c	[dʒ]	ج	Ж ж	⋈
5	Ç ç	[tʃ]	چ	Ч ч	⋈
6	D d	[d]	د	Д д	⋈
7	E e	[e]	ه	Е е	⋈
8	Ə ə	[æ]	أ	Ә ә	⋈
9	F f	[f]	ف	Ф ф	1
10	G g	[g]	گ	Г г	⋈

11	Ğ ğ	[ɣ]	غ	Ғ ғ	ƒ
12	H h	[h]	ھ	Һ һ	Ƨ
13	X x	[χ]	خ	Х х	Ҳ
14	I i	[ɯ]	اي	Ы ы	Ɑ
15	İ i	[i]	إي	И и	Ɱ
16	J j	[ʒ]	ژ	Ж ж	Ɐ
17	K k	[k]	ك	К к	Ǝ
18	Q q	[q]	ق	Қ қ	Ɒ
19	L l	[l]	ل	Л л	Ǝ
20	M m	[m]	م	М м	ⱱ
21	N n	[n]	ن	Н н)
22	Ñ ñ	[ɲ]	ڭ	Ң ң	Ǝ
23	O o	[o]	ئو	О о	Ǝ
24	Ö ö	[ø]	ئو	Ө ө	Ⱳ
25	P p	[p]	پ	П п	1
26	R r	[r]	ر	Р р	Ǝ
27	S s	[s]	س	С с	

28	Ş ş	[ʃ]	ش	Ш ш	Ɲ
29	T t	[t]	ت	Т т	ƚ
30	U u	[u]	ئو	У у	ƞ
31	Ū ū	[ʊ]	او	Ў ў	ƞ̄
32	Ü ü	[y]	أو	У у	ƞ̄
33	V v	[v]	و	В в	ƞ̄
34	Y y	[j]	ي	Й й	ƞ̄
35	Z z	[z]	ز	З з	ƞ̄
36	0		0	0	0
37	1		1	1	1
38	2		2	2	2
39	3		3	3	3
40	4		4	4	4
41	5		5	5	5
42	6		6	6	6
43	7		7	7	7
44	8		8	8	8
45	9		9	9	9

46	`		`	`	`
47	!		!	!	!
48	@		@	@	@
49	#		#	#	#
50	\$		\$	\$	\$
51	%		%	%	%
52	^		^	^	^
53	&		&	&	&
54	*		*	*	*
55	((([
56)))]
57	-		-	-	-
58	-		-	-	-
59	+		+	+	+
60	{		{	{	{
61	}		}	}	}
62	[[[[[
63]]]]]

64	:		:	:	:
65	;		;	;	;
66	“		“	“	“
67	‘		‘	‘	‘
68	<		<	<	<
69	>		>	>	>
70	/		/	/	/
71	\		\	\	\
72	,		,	,	,